

respect to θ such that the equations for Subscript $\mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}}$ and $\mathcal{U}_{g_{\downarrow a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \sim}}$ both equal Ω . This would allow us to solve for the unknowns in the equation and find the solution to P Vs . NP.

$$\mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} = \Omega - \mathcal{U}_{g_{\downarrow a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \sim}}$$

Then, we can solve the integral :

$$\mathbb{N} \, d\theta = \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} = \Omega - \mathcal{U}_{g_{\downarrow a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \sim}}$$

The solution is given by :

$$\mathbb{N} = \int \exists \infty \ni :$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} = \Omega - \mathcal{U}_{g_{\downarrow a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \sim}} \, d\theta = \Omega\theta + C$$

$$\mathcal{U} \langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \rangle = \ni \circ \langle \theta, \lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle \ni \mathbb{Z} \langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle = \ni \Omega \langle \upsilon, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle$$

$$\ni \mathbb{K} \langle \omega, \Theta, \Lambda, M \rangle$$

$$\ni \mathbb{P} \langle \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma \rangle$$

$$\ni \Omega \langle \Upsilon, \Phi, X, \Psi \rangle . \mathcal{U} \langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \rangle =$$

$$\circ \langle \theta, \lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle \ni \mathbb{Z} \langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle = \Omega \langle \upsilon, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle$$

$$\ni \mathbb{K} \langle \omega, \Theta, \Lambda, M \rangle$$

$$\ni \mathbb{P} \langle \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma \rangle$$

$$\ni \Omega \langle \Upsilon, \Phi, X, \Psi \rangle .$$

The integral is equal to the limit of the

sum of the terms of the series as infinity tends

to n : Subscript $[\mathcal{L}, \text{Subscript}[f, \uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta]] =$

$$\Omega - \sum \text{Subscript}[\mathcal{U}, \text{Subscript}[g, \downarrow a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \sim]] \, d\theta^n = \Omega\theta + C$$

$$\mathcal{U} \langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \rangle = \ni \circ \langle \theta, \lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle \ni \mathbb{Z} \langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle = \ni \Omega \langle \upsilon, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle$$

$$\ni \mathbb{K} \langle \omega, \Theta, \Lambda, M \rangle$$

$$\ni \mathbb{P} \langle \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma \rangle$$

$$\ni \Omega \langle \Upsilon, \Phi, X, \Psi \rangle$$

as $n \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$.